

Pest resistance — insects

Development of a brown planthopper (BPH) biotype and change in varietal resistance in Mekong Delta

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In 1988 wet season, we collected three new BPH *Nilaparvata lugens* Stal populations developed from BPH biotype 2 on rice variety OM80 at Omon district, northern Haugiang Province, and on IR64 at Chauthanh and Phutan districts, central and northeast Angiang Province, in the Mekong Delta. IR64 (or OM89) was introduced to farmers in 1983 and OM80 in 1984. Their BPH resistance was broken by a new BPH population in 4-5 yr.

We tested for biotype identification and screened varieties by the standard seedbox test. Test lines were sown in 20-cm-long rows at 30 seeds/row in 60- × 40- × 10-cm wood seedboxes filled 5 cm deep with fine soil, in a randomized complete block design with three replications.

Seedlings were infested 7 d after seeding with second- to third-instar BPH nymphs at 5-8 nymphs/plant. Damage was scored when 95% of susceptible check TN1 had died.

Varieties with no resistance gene or with *Bph 1* gene were very susceptible or

Table 1. Reaction of differential check varieties to new BPH population.^a CLRRI, 1988 wet season.

Variety	Gene for BPH resistance	Reaction to BPH populations			
		Chauthanh (Angiang)	Phutan (Angiang)	Omon (Haugiang)	CLRRI (Biotype 2)
TN1	None	9	9	9	9
IR8	None	9	9	9	9
IR28	<i>Bph 1</i>	7	7	7	7
IR30	<i>Bph 1</i>	5	7	7	7
IR36	<i>bph 2</i>	7	5	3	1
IR38	<i>bph 2</i>	5	3	1	3
Ptb 33	digenic	1	3	1	1

^aAv of 3 replications, by the *Standard evaluation system for rice*

Table 2. Comparison of reaction of modern varieties to old and new BPH populations. CLRRI, 1988 wet season.

Variety	Year introduced	Reaction	
		Old population Omon, 1988	New population Angiang, 1989
MTL 61 (IR19728-9-3-2)	1986	1	5
MTL 58 (IR13240-108-2-2-3)	1986	3	7
OM87-1 (IR31802-48-2-2-2)	1987	1	5
OM86-9 (IR74) (IR32429-47-3-2-2)	1986	-	5
OM606-1-1-1-1 (IR42/Tran chau lun)	1989	3	5
OM87-9 (IR31868-64-2-3-3)	1987	3	5
OM576-18-1-1 (Hungary/IR42)	1988	3	5
OM296 (Than nong do/IR48)	1989	0	3
OM44-5 (OM90/OM80)	1889	0	3
NN4B (IR42)	1982	5	7
IR64 (IR18348-36-3-3)	1983	1	5
IR66 (IR32307-107-3-2-2)	1986	3	5
IR68 (IR28224-3-2-3-2)	1989	1	5
IR70 (IR28228-12-3-1)	1989	1	5
CR94-12 (resistant check)		0	5
IR36 (resistant check)		1	5
TN1 (susceptible check)		9	9

susceptible to all new BPH populations; varieties with *bph 2* were attacked by the BPH population in Angiang (damage rating 5-7) but were still resistant to the BPH population in Haugiang (Table 1). Ptb 33 with digenic resistance genes was resistant to all new BPH populations.

BPH virulence appears to have shifted higher than that of BPH biotype 2 in Angiang.

Most varieties resistant to BPH biotype 2 were moderately susceptible to the new biotype (Angiang population) (Table 2). ■

Stress tolerance — drought

Genetic variability in midday leaf water potential (LWP) of irrigated rice

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In rice, midday LWP falls, even in irrigated rice, because of a lag between water absorption by roots and transpira-

tion through the leaves. This indicates that midday LWP may be a criterion to use in selecting for drought resistance.

We grew six advanced upland breeding lines and two varieties under irrigated field conditions in 1988 dry season to evaluate genetic variability in midday LWP.

Experimental 5- × 5-m plots were laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications. At maximum tillering, the LWP of 10

penultimate, fully expanded leaves of each variety in each replication were measured at 1200-1300 h under clear skies, using standard pressure chamber technique.

Differences among varieties were significant (see table). The highest LWP was in BR4290-3-1-10, the lowest in BR4290-3-3-5. The differential LWP observed suggests that LWP may be used as a drought resistance selection criterion. ■

Leaf water potential (LWP) of upland rice breeding lines and varieties in an irrigated field in Gazipur, Bangladesh, 1988.

Variety or line	LWP (MPa)
BR4290-3-1-10	- 0.75
BR4290-3-3-5	- 1.24
BR1888-29-2-2-3	- 1.00
BR1888-29-2-3-4	- 1.00
BR1890-12-2-1-1	- 1.11
BR1890-1-1-1-2	- 1.14
BR20	- 0.90
BR21	- 0.92
<i>F-test</i>	184.42**
LSD (0.05)	0.04

Stress tolerance — excess water

Germination and seedling development of floating rice at different soil moisture regimes

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Farmers usually dry seed floating rices before the onset of monsoon rains. In certain years, when the monsoon is early, dry seeding is not possible. Also, dry seeding is followed by drought, and farmers may have to replant a wet seeded rice.

We studied germination and growth of floating rice under different moisture regimes at crop establishment. Dry seeds and pregerminated seeds of Pin Gaew 56, a Thai floating rice, were planted at 100 seeds/tray in 25- × 33- × 10-cm plastic trays filled with 7 kg Maahas clay soil. Four soil moisture regimes were applied, with three replications (see table).

The pregerminated seeds emerged first. However, differences in percentage

Emergence of Pin Gaew 56 seedlings under different soil moisture regimes.^a IRRI greenhouse, 1990.

Soil moisture	Emergence (%) at 7 DAS	
	Dry seed	Pregerminated seed
Field capacity	98 a	98 a
Saturated	95 ab	95 ab
2 cm clear water	67 c	87 b
2 cm muddy water	71 c	74 c

^aIn a column, values followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

of emergence between dry seeds and pregerminated seeds 7 d after sowing (DAS) were small. Field capacity and saturated soil moisture favored seedling emergence. As little as 2 cm excess water significantly decreased emergence. Pregerminated seeds emerged poorly in muddy water.

Growth and development were vigorous at field capacity and at saturation (see figure). However, seedlings from pregerminated seeds tended to grow and develop better in saturated soil than at field capacity. Standing 2-cm-deep water significantly retarded seedling growth and development.

The effects were more-pronounced in seedlings from dry seed than from pregerminated seed. Muddy water at seeding did not have much effect on growth and development at later stages because the water cleared within 24 h.

The results indicate that field capacity or saturated soil moisture regime is favorable for germination, growth, and development of both dry and pregerminated seeds. Broadcasting dry seeds of floating rice is recommended, but pregerminated seeds could be an alternative in very wet or extremely low areas where rainwater accumulates during sowing. ■

Shoot and root dry weight of rice seedlings germinated under different soil moisture regimes. IRRI greenhouse, 1990.

Stress tolerance — adverse temperature

Screening rice cultivars at reproductive stage for low temperature tolerance in western Nepal

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Injury due to low temperature is a major constraint to improvement of rice production in the 1,000-2,000 m high areas of Nepal. No improved variety has yet been developed for elevations above 1,400 m.

In 1987 and 1988, we evaluated rice cultivars at three altitudes. The materials

were from IRRI; the National Rice Improvement Programme (NRIP), Parwanipur; Department of Agricultural Botany (DOAB); and local germplasm collected from 1,000-2,300 m altitudes in the western hills.

In 1987, the materials were evaluated at Tapu (1,000 m), Lumle (1,400 m), and Chhomro (2,000 m) to identify varietal differences in low temperature tolerance and altitude and the highest limit of varietal adaptation. In 1988, materials identified as promising from the 1987 trials were assessed at Tapu. Sera (1,250 m), and Lumle. Test cultivars were planted in rows in 1.2-m² plots, at 20- ×